

HUMAN COMMON, AND THE PROVISIONS OF WAR AND EUTHANASIA IN RELIGIONS

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Abstract

The difference between human beings has delayed the historical course of man for many centuries. All wars in our history are caused by differences, although differences do not always lead to wars. However, war has one cause, which is difference, the difference that develops the will of superiority in the strong, so war occurs, and the strong crushes the weak, according to an animal tradition in its origin. It is worth noting that the Arab world has been suffering for years from grave violations of the laws and rules of war stipulated in the Geneva Conventions. A cursory look at the state of armed conflicts and the methods of fighting will reveal an appalling level of human suffering. In these ongoing conflicts over the past years, thousands have died, including a large number of the civilian population, while millions have been forced to seek refuge or internal displacement due to the fighting. For those who survived, luck was not gracious, as thousands were crammed into camps; it lacks a minimum of respect for human dignity. The importance of the topic of this research is reflected in its presentation of the major issues, which formed points of agreement between civilizations. In addition to this study; deliberately presenting the texts according to a precise scientific method. We will answer through this research about the seriousness of killing and how conflicts are formed? Where are the nations' efforts manifested? What are the repercussions of war on common humanity? How did religious texts deal with the life of the human soul? Where are the religious rulings for the sanctity of the human soul manifested in life? The analytical method is the main method in this study, by extrapolating the texts from their original sources, and trying to understand their historical context. Relying on research and specialized studies on the subject, with the analysis of the ideas and interpretations of academic researchers, and commenting as a final stage to address and answer the research problem.

Keywords: Common Humanity, Murder, Spirit, Holiness, Religions

INTRODUCTION

Contrary to what was expected, it did not mark the end of the Cold War and bipolar global politics; to the beginning of the era of peace and development¹. Instead, from the 1980s until today, the world has seen a massive increase in violent conflict, which, more than anything else, can be described with enormous human and societal costs; in the form of injuries, displacement, looting and destruction of property².

One consequence of this shift was; in history is the increasing human participation in conflict situations, by the international community. Including, UN specialized agencies, international NGOs, national NGOs and state administrations, whose operations have at the same time expanded in the size and scope of the mandate. But the changes that the international community has undergone are not just about scaling up traditional processes. New types of warfare required major organizational and operational adjustments³.

I will focus on only one dimension of this process, which is the changing relationship between war and murder and the common humanity. I suggest that since humanity is founded on an idea; to be substantial and essential. The true relationship of humanitarian

organizations with violence is crucial to their self-understanding, and to their broader legitimization in society. Thus, it deserves in-depth study⁴.

Also at the level of religions; we know what Moses brought, Jesus brought it, and Muhammad, the master of the messengers, sealed with it, may God's prayers and peace be upon them all. And from above seven heavens, God, Blessed and exalted be He, addressed His Prophet Muhammad, saying: "The Messenger believes in what has been sent down to him from his Lord, and [so do] believers. They all believe in God and His angels, His scriptures, and His messengers. They say, 'We do not differentiate between any of His messengers. We hear and obey. Grant us your forgiveness, Lord, to you we shall all return!'"⁵ We worship one God, who willed for us to be different, and heavenly messages all came to make humanity happy and all stipulated the sanctity of blood, the Almighty said: "And if your Lord had willed, He would have made people one nation, and they will still differ"⁶. We know that everyone has known God since before the foundation of the world. Since all life is for the purposes of God, and all human souls are equally sacred, we believe that human life is blessed by God and should be preserved and nurtured.

Repercussions of the wars⁷

Talk about the current accepted definition of war crimes; as a general concept: serious violations of the laws or customs of international or internal armed conflict. Committed in the context of an armed conflict, in circumstances requiring the punishment of the criminal offender⁸. Although serious, it often accompanies descriptions of violations that are war crimes⁹. Describing the violation as serious; it is the objective that must be discovered in the process of determining the war crime at the end of this research.¹⁰ Meaning any violation identified is said to be serious and therefore a war crime. Provided the behavior is intentional, it is punishable by criminal law.¹¹

Therefore, the question arises: What makes the conduct such a grave violation that it constitutes a war crime? The answer is to consider violations of the laws and customs of war grave; Exposing protected persons or protected objects to danger¹².

Prosecute persons who commit or order grave breaches of the Geneva Conventions of August 12, 1949. Acts directed; against persons or property protected under the provisions of the Geneva Convention relating to willful killing. And torture or inhuman treatment, including biological experiments. Intentionally causing great suffering or serious injury to body or health. And mass destruction and appropriation of property without military necessity justifying it.

And forcing a prisoner of war or a civilian to serve in the forces of an enemy state. And deliberately depriving a prisoner of war or a civilian of his right to a fair and regular trial. And unlawful deportation, transfer, or unlawful confinement of a civilian. Civilians were taken hostage.¹³

It is possible to he take a view the debate on the scope of application of the concept of grave violations; for being it does not give way to a straightforward solution. But this is the case when one gets lost in the legal jungle, and the intricacies of the four Geneva

Conventions of 1949, and their Additional Protocols of 1977. There are reasons in those instruments to claim, that the grave breaches are war crimes. It may not be committed. Except in international armed conflicts. This proposal is controversial.¹⁴

Nevertheless, we cite stronger reasons for the conclusion; To take the view that grave violations are limited to international armed conflicts is to neglect the purpose of international humanitarian law as a whole. It is about protecting the basic values of humanity. Humanity remains the same, no matter where it is; in the high-tech war fields. In which the major Western powers participate, against each other or against other countries. As well as in the jungle of an African or Asian country; involved in a civil war. A serious violation of international humanitarian law is considered a grave violation in both cases. It is easy to see if the protection of humanity; It is the goal of international humanitarian law, as it should be. Or that there are other goals.

We add; the triumph of humanity aids in that discussion, particularly on the usual requirement, that the treaty be interpreted in good faith. According to the ordinary meaning, which must be given to the terms of the treaty in their context, and in the light of its object and purpose. The simple meaning should not be detracted from here. As for the circumstances in which treaties are drafted. They often lead to inconsistent wording, and care must be taken when giving weight to differences in terminology. The translator himself is likely to find a distortion of the passages if he imagines that their formulation is sealed by the infallibility of Pertulosa Claim¹⁵.

How are human conflicts formed?

Competition and conflict between and within cultures, for food or a place to live, is essential in the process of evolution, and thus intrinsic to our biology¹⁶. But like many other animals, we are also social beings. And like them; we developed behaviours, to avoid the harmful effects of excessive intra-species violence. These include singing rituals or fighting performances, and acts of submission or matchmaking¹⁷.

We ask the following questions: Do people, or perhaps only males, have a developed tendency to kill members of other groups? Not just an ability to kill, but an innate tendency to take up arms, directing them toward mass violence? The word "community" is the key. People fight and kill for personal reasons, but killing is not war. War is social, where groups are organized, to kill people from other groups. The controversy is taking place today. On the historical roots of the war around two polar locations¹⁸. In one, war is an evolving tendency to eliminate any potential rivals¹⁹. In this scenario, the humans were all the way, like the animal always waging war for dominance.

The other position holds that armed conflict only emerged during the last millennia, when changing social conditions provided; Motivation and organization for mass murder. The two sides are separated by what the late anthropologist Keith Otterbein²⁰ called: hawks and doves. This controversy is also related to; on the question of whether the instinctive, warlike inclinations of an animal can be detected²¹.

The groups of which we consider ourselves a part are important to our understanding of ourselves and the classification of others or external groups; these groups often form the

basis of conflict. Groups can have countless or unlimited identities. First was certainly kin, and then race, but as societies grew, groups defined themselves in more complex ways. Our sense of group influences the way we see and feel about the world around us. We are more likely to sympathize with those in our own group, and more likely to dehumanize outside groups²².

Groups based on religious or sacred values can increase group dependence and cooperation through costly rituals. It can also; Inspiring irrational sacrifices. Whereas, rational social contracts seem less able to inspire such intense loyalty²³.

If the war expresses an innate tendency, then we have to find evidence that proves that the war was in small societies, through archaeological studies, especially prehistoric. Having already found such evidence, in archaeologist Stephen LeBlanc²⁴ and colleagues' book: When there is a good archaeological picture of any society on Earth, there is always evidence of war as well. Perhaps 25 percent of war deaths is a conservative estimate. Evolutionary psychologists argue that, with casualties of this scale, war was a mechanism of natural selection in which the fittest prevailed, to gain both mates and resources²⁵.

This perspective has achieved wide influence. The political scientist Francis Fukuyama²⁶ wrote: The roots of recent wars and genocide go back tens or hundreds of thousands of years among our ancestors, who were dependent on hunting and gathering, even with animals. Bradley Thayer²⁷, a leading scholar of international relations, argues that evolutionary theory explains why the instinctive tendency, to protect one's tribe, turns, over time, into collectivist tendencies toward xenophobia and ethnocentrism in international relations. If wars are a natural outbreak of instinctive hatred, why do we look for other answers? If human nature is inclined towards the mass murder of strangers, how long can we avoid it?

Our interest in the conflict, must ultimately be the facilitation of peace. There are many examples of neighboring societies, which do not fight against each other. Containing a common identity with other groups, turning outsiders inward, appears to provide an effective way to overcome conflict. Although some regimes (the European Union) still fight offshore entities, others (the Orang Asli communities in Malaysia) do not²⁸. We hope that understanding how human societies overcome adversity and develop peaceful relationships will help chart a course for a less violent future.

Humans have a clear capacity to engage in wars, but their brains are not recruited; to identify outsiders involved in group conflicts. According to these arguments; deadly mass attacks appeared, when hunter-gatherer societies grew in size and complexity, and later with the birth of agriculture. Archeology, supplemented by observations of contemporary hunter-gatherer cultures, allows us to determine the times. To some extent, the social conditions that led to the emergence and intensification of wars.

What are the efforts of countries to repel wars?

The challenge of deterring regional aggression many decades ago; it is an afterthought in the United Nations strategy towards most regions of the world, and is gaining renewed importance²⁹.

The preamble to the Charter of the United Nations states³⁰ that the primary objective of the Organization is: to save future generations from the scourge of war. Therefore, as stated in the report, the sustainability of peace should be seen as an essential component³¹.

However, UN responses remain overly focused on addressing the symptoms of conflicts, rather than addressing the root causes. As a result, peacebuilding responses are largely underfunded, neglected and underachieved. This can be attributed to the lack of systematic and coordinated planning and business segmentation³².

The basis for the results of deterrence - the initial and, in some respects, decisive variable - is provided by the motivations of the aggressor. Unmotivated attackers are easy to deter. Those who are intensely motivated and whose level of threat perception can reach paranoia may be impossible to deter. This is a wake-up call for UN member states to be part of the solution. Make United Nations peacebuilding engagements more effective³³.

The first step towards enhancing deterrence is to: manage the motivations of the potential aggressor. Required to do so; often compromises. As well as measures to shape the surrounding geopolitical context, to allay its fears and increase the political costs of aggression³⁴.

Scientific support for peacebuilding depends today; mainly on the social understanding of identity politics. An unknown stranger can become a hated enemy, or a helpful friend. Tribalism, nationalism, racism, and prejudice based on language and religion are inferential methods by which we define we and they, especially in times of economic decline and limited resources.

The backbone of conflict prevention lies in connection theory, a social phenomenon identified by Gordon Allport in the 1950s, which posits that positive communication between people is one of opposing identities. It reduces prejudice between them (under certain circumstances). It is the idea of making a friend, which can change your view of their community.³⁵

The theory of peacebuilding has also remained largely unchanged, with subsequent research building on the idea of this social perspective. And therefore; Impact assessment in the peacebuilding space is largely based on self-reported questionnaires by participants.³⁶

The repercussions of the war on the common humanity:

A perfect storm of converging trends in the world wars is changing the way the ICRC, must think about helping those caught up in conflict.

The ICRC works in more than 80 countries around the world. She sees for herself the suffering of people, and of communities caught in the crossfire of war and violence. The committee's budget, and staffing, has nearly doubled over the past two years, and this growth has been supported by major donors.³⁷

The Committee works in accordance with the principles of neutral, impartial and independent humanitarian action. Working for; Finding practical solutions for people in

very difficult circumstances. It negotiates humanitarian spaces by consensus of parties to conflict, brokering agreements to provide assistance, and working in close proximity to people who might come under fire. It deals with warring parties to respect international humanitarian law. The main places it operates include: Syria, Iraq, Yemen, Afghanistan and Myanmar. And of course some of the major African contexts, and some of the countries neighboring the mentioned conflict areas. Recently, urban violence contexts have become a growing concern for the humanitarian sector.³⁸

Humanitarian aid can help increase violence in conflicts. If these resources are diverted, they can be used to purchase weapons. Thus, the conflict is exacerbated. Aid recipients (whether they are the civilian population or the detainees) may become a target for armed groups, trying to obtain relief supplies. This abuse takes many forms, pressure or harassment of aid recipients to give up part of the assistance they received. Such as their threat of forced recruitment of young people, or even the displacement of entire populations, by armed groups when food distributions drive large groups to assemble. Or detention of large groups of civilians; Hostages so that they can be used as bait for humanitarian aid, which is then embezzled by armed groups. And direct attacks on people receiving the assistance (looting and killing). And the attacks on humanitarian aid convoys and warehouses.³⁹

We add that humanitarian aid is often an alternative; on the measures that the warring parties themselves should take, to help those parties evade their responsibilities. In the case of weakening the state, humanitarian aid directly contributes to aggravating the situation, in particular; by setting up a parallel economy or a non-governmental health care system run by aid organizations. This effect is even more serious. When it happens in a country, it is already in the process of collapse. Because it accelerates that breakdown, and increases the risk of unrestrained violence.⁴⁰

And also; Human activity is seen as a non-political, charitable and beneficial act. It targets anyone in distress and need. And humanitarian organizations confront new wars, while fighting them on the ground. It is becoming increasingly difficult to maintain the basic distinction between violence and humanity. As a result, humanitarian projects have come under increasing criticism, and some of their innocence has been lost. At the same time, it can be accused of complicity in generating structural violence.⁴¹

The sanctity of life in the monotheistic religions:

In 1981 at the General Council in Anaheim, California, members of the Christian and Missionary Alliance adopted a Statement on Abortion.⁴² This statement, representing the consensus of the sect, affirmed the historical Christian belief that life begins at conception. She expressed her opposition to abortion on demand, as a violation of human dignity and God's moral law. The exception is made only when the mother's life is threatened⁴³. Individual life is sacred in the Christian religion, not to mention mass murder.

First: the sanctity of life in the Bible:

We know through the Word of God that every individual has been known by God, since before the foundation of the world; We read: "Then the word of the LORD came unto me, saying, Before I formed thee in the belly I knew thee; and before thou camest forth out of the womb I sanctified thee, and I ordained thee a prophet unto the nations"⁴⁴, and "For thou hast possessed my reins: thou hast covered me in my mother's womb"⁴⁵. I will praise thee; for I am fearfully and wonderfully made⁴⁶: marvellous are thy works; and that my soul knoweth right well.⁴⁷ My substance was not hid from thee, when I was made in secret, and curiously wrought in the lowest parts of the earth⁴⁸. Thine eyes did see my substance, yet being unperfect; and in thy book all my members were written, which in continuance were fashioned, when as yet there was none of them. How precious also are thy thoughts unto me, O God! How great is the sum of them!⁴⁹.⁵⁰ God, according to a Psalm, declared his blessing on the life of the child: "Lo, children are a heritage of the LORD: and the fruit of the womb is his reward. As arrows are in the hand of a mighty man; so are children of the youth. Happy is the man that hath his quiver full of them: they shall not be ashamed, but they shall speak with the enemies in the gate"⁵¹ ⁵², Since all life exists for the purposes of God and all human souls are equally sacred, we believe that the life of an unborn child is blessed by God and should be preserved and nurtured. Therefore, the Christian and Missionary Alliance opposes induced abortion.

Since then, the debate in the United States about the value of human life has remained unabated. The division deepened between those who hold human life sacred, and those who value human life on the basis of function or material qualities. As a result, additional threats to the dignity and sanctity of human life have arisen. Arguments about the intrinsic value of human life now include euthanasia.⁵³ And questions regarding both self- and assisted suicide. Some utilitarian philosophers have openly justified; The killing of newborns, unwanted or deprived. In the face of the increasing secular materialism, militant atheism, and moral relativism that accompany these erroneous views of human existence. It is now necessary for Christians who are committed to the authority of God's word and the truth of the gospel to reaffirm the sanctity and value of human life. This assertion is based on clear testimony from the Bible. Moreover, it corresponds to two thousand years of Christian witness.⁵⁴

End of life issues:

Since human life is a sacred gift from God, ending a life, by way of euthanasia, suicide or assisted suicide, is morally and biblically unacceptable.⁵⁵

Mercy killing; It is the intentional act of killing a person with an incurable disease or injury. The decision to remove life support devices from a terminally ill patient is not generally understood as such a noble act. Euthanasia and the removal of life support devices are two different things in their nature. The first is the deliberate act of ending life, and the second is not to artificially prolong life. It may be legitimate to discontinue medical procedures that are stressful, dangerous, unusual, or disproportionate to the expected outcome. Through advances in medical technology, doctors are now able to extend the lives of patients by artificial means. The fact that such innovative means are available

does not create a moral imperative to extend life indefinitely. Family members are often asked to make decisions about extending a loved one's life. These decisions are difficult to make. It requires careful thought in the Bible, as well as consultation with pastors, medical personnel, and sometimes legal experts.⁵⁶

God asserts his sovereignty over all human life in Deuteronomy 39:32: "See now that I, even I, am he, and there is no god with me: I kill, and I make alive; I wound, and I heal: neither is there any that can deliver out of my hand"⁵⁷; this is what determines longevity. A willingness to submit to physical death is God's timing for death. Coupled with the realization that this is not the end of life. It is a transition from life on earth to life in glory. The absence of the body means being with God.⁵⁸

Jesus' command to love others, and care for those who suffer, does not allow followers of Christ to be unconcerned or arrogant about those who suffer suffering and misery. Compassion for those who are weak or sick compels believers to seek relief from their pain, as the Bible itself does. James directs believers to anoint and pray, for the sick, and to look after their physical need⁵⁹. However, in doing so, Christians must acknowledge the spiritual dimension of human life, recognizing that God can use pain, for ultimate spiritual benefit and, through this, for His glory. As the Apostle Paul wrote to the Corinthians, so we do not despair. Although outside we are wasting, inside we are renewing day by day. Because our light and momentary troubles bring us eternal glory far above them all. Therefore, we do not fix our eyes on what is seen, but on what is invisible, because what is seen is temporary, but what is invisible is eternal.⁶⁰

Secondly, the sanctity of life in Islam:

The scholars emphasized that the Islamic religion enjoined the protection of places of worship and the security of those who frequent them, and the sanctity of the human soul, whatever its religion or color, and that the security and care of the other in the Islamic society; They are among the constants of Islamic Sharia, demanding humanity; All denominations united and not dispersed.

The Islamic religion has decided to protect the people of dhimmis and the trustees as long as they are in the home of Islam, and in that the Messenger of God, peace and blessings be upon him, says: "Except for him who wronged a treatie or charged him beyond his capacity, or took something without his consent, I will argue with him on the Day of Resurrection"⁶¹. And laying the foundations for cooperation and communication between God made their food lawful for nations, so he said: "And the food of those who were given the Book is lawful for you, and your food is lawful for them"⁶². Islam also forbids aggression against the human soul, but what is happening now in the world is inconsistent with the principles of Islamic Sharia, from the need to protect the human soul, and not to attack others.

Islam also called us to believe in all the messengers, without fanaticism. Our Master Muhammad, may God's prayers and peace be upon him, depicted for us the sanctity, greatness, and status of the human soul when he circumambulated the honorable Kaaba.⁶³He says: "How great you are, how great is your holiness, how beautiful you are, and how beautiful your perfume is, and the believer is more sacred to God than you are his

blood, money and dignity⁶⁴. And the matter of the sanctity of the human soul is not limited to the order of man protecting it. In this way only, but it preserves the sanctity of the soul, even if it is non-Muslim and even if it is not affiliated with the religion of Islam.

An edematous person says about him, the Messenger of God, may God bless him and grant him peace: Whoever harms an edematous, I will be his opponent on the Day of Resurrection⁶⁵. And God Almighty says: "God does not forbid you on behalf of those who did not fight you on account of religion and did not expel you from your homes that you treat them kindly and treat them justly, for God loves those who are just"⁶⁶. Rather, the Messenger, may God bless him and grant him peace, made it clear that he is innocent of those who assaulted the sanctity of the soul of non-Muslims, and from the people of safety. And the covenant with those who do not fight us, says: "Except for him who wrongs a covenant, or detracts from him, or takes something from him without the consent of his soul, then I will plead with him on the Day of Resurrection⁶⁷".

Asking for love and approbation:

The Almighty says: "And do not kill the soul that God has forbidden except with truth"⁶⁸. This necessitated that there should be continuous and continuous efforts, in order to deepen the spirit of brotherhood of faith, and instill the teachings of religion in the souls of humanity. The Holy Qur'an and the pure Sunnah are full of texts that call for love and benevolence. in the Almighty's saying: "The believers are but brothers, so make peace between your two brothers and fear God that you may receive mercy." And brotherhood here is the brotherhood of religion.⁶⁹ The Islamic religion accommodates other religions, recognizes them and sanctifies the rights of their followers; Almighty says: "And say to the people well"⁷⁰. And that the Muslim knows that they are closer to us, you will find that the bitterest in their enmity to the faithful are the Jews and the polytheists; and the nearest in affection to them are those who say, 'We are Christians.' That is because there are priests and monks among them; and because they are free from pride.

The purpose of Islam was not only to stop harming the brothers of religion, but rather to be kind to them. The Muslim should not stop at the mere recitation or chanting of these verses, but rather he should apply them in practice. Hence, every believer must abide by the teachings of religion, because they contain the infallibility of blood and the safety of souls. And that the religious institution, the media, civil society organizations, education and education popularize the culture of brotherhood and citizenship among all mankind.

Document coexistence in Medina:

Egyptian society as a model; More than 1400 years ago, when Amr ibn al-Aas conquered Egypt. The Copts remained the vast majority of Egypt for a long time.⁷¹ Egypt has not forced anyone since the Islamic conquest to change their religion, and those who entered Islam from the Christians were of their own free will. Islam considers that there is no compulsion in religion, and the second fact in Islam, is the reality of pluralism, and diversity among humans in Belief, thought, culture and values.

As for the third fact, it is the freedom of Islam to choose. If God wanted all people to be Muslims, He would have done so. The Almighty says: "Had God pleased, He would have

united you in one community; but He lets go astray whoever He will, and guides whoever He will, and you will surely be called upon to account for all your actions”⁷². There is a verse that applies to the Messenger, peace and blessings be upon him, because he wanted all people to respond to the invitation, God Almighty says: “Perhaps you may destroy yourself with grief if they do not believe in this message.” This is the will of God Almighty, and Muslims must respect his will, and Egypt lived on this premise under the rule Islam, since Amr ibn al-Aas, in accordance with the Almighty’s saying: “So whoever wills, let him believe, and whoever wills, let him disbelieve”⁷³. And we must do as the Messenger, may God’s prayers and peace be upon him, did in Medina, so he lived with Muslims, Christians and Jews, and issued the Medina Document, which was the basis for this coexistence. Which states: They have what we have, and they have what we owe. This is how Muslims deal with others.

Talking about values and morals is a talk about man himself, and man in Islamic teachings has a special status, for God created man, and made him a caliph on earth. All the elements of succession were facilitated for him, in his honor. He also subjected to him everything in the universe, and creatures. In order for him to realize the meaning of honor and subjugation, because of the Almighty’s saying: “Have you not seen that God has subdued for you all that is in the heavens and all that is on the earth?”⁷⁴ And this subjugation and subjugation of God, by His majesty is the status of a human being, and his dignity; the almighty says: “And we have honored the Children of Adam, carried them by land and sea, and provided them with good things”⁷⁵.

In view of this; the divine legislation was emphasizing the preservation of the human soul, calling for its revival, and warning against attacking it, or causing its demise. A form of the general form, by mentioning the human soul in the indefinite form preceded by the relative noun “who”, and all of that is one of the forms that benefit the generality. It also came in an eloquent legislative manner that includes all forms of murder, abuse and assault on humans. God almighty says: “That was why We laid it down for the Children of Israel that whoever killed a human being—except as a punishment for murder or for spreading corruption in the land— shall be regarded as having killed all mankind, and that whoever saved a human life shall be regarded as having saved all mankind. Our messengers came to them with clear signs, but many of them continued to commit excesses in the land”⁷⁶. Looking at the differences between faith and non-belief. The principle is the sanctity of human blood, and exposure to it is not permitted.

The divine statement was not limited to this text that legislates, to protect and preserve human blood, but the Qur’anic texts related to this matter. Which legislated to preserve the human soul from any aggression, as one of the five necessities, and as one of the overall Islamic goals. Preserving oneself and protecting oneself from any aggression was a high Islamic morality, and it was called upon. And a goal that Sharia seeks to achieve, and its preservation - according to Al-Shatibi - is based on two things: One: securing everything that establishes its pillars and establishes its rules. This is due to the aspect of existence. The second: related to what prevents it from the actual or expected imbalance, taking into account the aspect of nothingness.⁷⁷ This means; The wasting of safe and secure blood, excessive commotion or murder, and the practice of actions that

lead to the targeting of the infallible human soul, are among the actions that are contrary to Islamic morals, and to the purposes of the reputable Sharia. Thus, it is one of the morals and evils that should be prevented.

The ethical principles in Islamic law stipulate that human life is a gift from God - the Almighty - to man. And this life, no one has the right to take it away, without the will of God. In view of that; an attack on an individual's life without a legitimate right was an attack on the whole of society, exposing him to chaos, instability and security. On the other hand, the offender was punished with qisas; It is a revival of the whole society, and the establishment of the pillars of security and stability in it, as the Almighty says: "That was why We laid it down for the Children of Israel that whoever killed a human being shall be regarded as having killed all mankind, and that whoever saved a human life shall be regarded as having saved all mankind. Our messengers came to them with clear signs, but many of them continued to commit excesses in the land"⁷⁸.

And since the human soul is infallible in the religion of Islam, and human blood enjoys a great respect and a severe sanctity, God Almighty compared between unjust killing and polytheism, in his dear book: "those who never invoke any other deity besides God, nor take a life which God has made sacred, except with the right to do so, nor commit adultery. Anyone who does that shall face punishment"⁷⁹.

The infallibility of the nation lies in its unity, and the preservation of its original values. Considering that preserving the nation's unity is a moral and religious duty. And that the heavenly messages in their purity, purity and essence are one, and their source is one, and they all strive to achieve human happiness, freedom and dignity. And that the heavenly religions criminalize the assault on the human soul.

The importance of the enlightenment and guiding scholars' role in finding ways to achieve the unity of the nation, by putting down these personal differences. And not to allow the fanatics to impose their ideas, which are tearing the nation apart and working to dismantle it. Also, scholars, thinkers, and the media have adopted a clear policy based on achieving unity and rejecting discord and disagreement. Achieving the unity of the class, which is considered one of the duties of the religion, and one of its foundations. And spreading the tolerant teachings of Islam, following the method of wisdom, and good exhortation in calling to God. How to live with the other, accept him, and respect his beliefs. A clear indication of the position of the human soul in Islam.

A unified vision of the major issues:

On the importance of religious discourse in burying sedition, it is a comprehensive confrontation of the cultural and intellectual invasion aimed at emptying the homeland of its content and presenting it to the world. Here comes the role of religious scholars, and opinion leaders, in identifying the shortcomings and removing them permanently. Work to promote and advance values. And remove the differences, the differences. To promote the values of tolerance and collective cooperation in society, and to confront all causes of sectarian or religious tension.

It has been decided by all the jurists of Sharia that the people of the dhimmis, the covenants, and the trustees are all bloodless, and that fighting and killing them is unanimously forbidden. Even the hadiths of the Prophet came to confirm that: assaulting the sanctity of these souls is a reason for depriving them of entering Paradise, and even of its smell. Accordingly, any aggression or harm to them is contrary to the religious teachings and morals stipulated.

The ethical dimension is also reflected in the sanctity of the human soul, through the vision of the Sharia, and its position on some practices that affect the human body and soul. For example, the prohibition of human aggression against himself. Whether that attack was by taking the soul directly - suicide - or by doing an action, which may lead to self-destruction or the demise of the soul. It is for a person to remove a part of his body, without a disease or a legitimate interest that accrues to him, because of the Almighty's saying: "And do not kill yourselves, for God has been merciful to you"⁸⁰. Then the soul of man is not his property, rather it is the property of his Creator, and man will be asked about it, has he preserved it? And he fulfilled her rights and duties, or did he lose her and assault her, and did not take into account the purposes of the Sharia, to achieve her interest and ward off corruption from her.

Among the great interest of Islam in the human soul is the imposition of many provisions that guarantee its protection and maintenance, and the matter It was not limited to natural conditions. Rather, it goes beyond it to include all exceptional cases; Such as the cases of fighting that take place between Muslims and others, so it was a goal of humanity, mercy and justice. We note this in many combative legislation, the most important of which are: What came about the protection of some victims of international conflicts, as the texts came to confirm that there are certain types of subjects belonging to the enemy warrior. It is not permissible to fight them and it is not permissible to attack them, and jurisprudential codes are abundant in many Examples of these types. The Islamic Sharia was thus a moral law, which preserves blood, and preserves souls even in its wars against its enemies.

Islamic morals reached its climax, when it decided its position on the sanctity of man even after death, where the battle dead - even if he was an enemy - was granted immunity, so that his physical dignity would be preserved from violation. It protects his envy from any idealization or distortion.

Among the issues in which the ethical dimension is most evident is what Islamic Sharia has decided; that dealing with enemy prisoners in a state of war is limited to "manna or redemption", emphasizing this; However, Islamic morals rejects assaulting prisoners by killing or harming, and not only that; Rather, feeding the captive, being courteous to him, and treating him kindly, became among the things that led to the praise of sincere believers.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Beware of attempts to sow discord, by the enemies of good. Sowing division and conflict among people, based on a discourse that confuses the enemy, the friend, and the dissenting opinion, and diverts consideration from the real battle, which is construction.

Regulating and developing the religious discourse that promotes a culture of tolerance, as an urgent necessity, and transforming it into an effective and distinguished discourse; it would qualify the nation to be a leader in human society.

The role that legitimate educational institutions can play; In correcting concepts, and forming a public opinion that is consistent with national values, away from all kinds of extremism.

CONCLUSION

There are many religious legislations that stipulate the inviolability of the human soul, but what concerns us from all of this is the assertion that all of these legislations highlight - beyond any doubt - the highness, humanity and greatness of religious morals, and that the religious legislative system is an entity that embodies this moral spirit, And that morality is the essence and spirit of religion in effect in all its legislation and parts. To the extent that we hardly find a single legislative provision, except that we find the moral dimension present in it.

Humanitarian aid remains essential, to help the victims of armed conflict to survive. It can affect the conflict itself - particularly its length and level of violence - for either better or worse. To minimize the negative impacts of humanitarian assistance, each case must be analyzed in detail, taking into account the social, economic and cultural context, in order to provide a response, tailored to needs while minimizing the undesirable effects of aid⁸¹. Such analysis requires access to the victims, and the best strategy for obtaining this is to consistently respect the fundamental principles of the Red Cross and Red Crescent, in particular, impartiality and neutrality. The relationship between humanitarian assistance and respect for the rules of international humanitarian law is essential to ensuring that those in need have access to treatment, food, water and normal means of production. In the event of a violation of humanitarian law, everything possible must be done to stop the violations immediately and to punish the perpetrators.

Notes

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- 2) taha, eabd alrahman, sual al'akhlaqi, aldaar albayda', almarkaz althaqafia alearabia, t 1, 2000, 14.
- 3) aleamiriu, 'abu alhasani, al'ielam bimanaqib al'iislami, alqahirata: dar alkitaab alearabii, 1387/ 1967, 78-79 (dirasat watahqi 'ahmad eabd alhamid ghrab).
- 4) Birgitte Refslund Sørensen, Violence and humanitarian assistance: Reflections on an intricate relationship, <https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/03F8145084D9731CC12571F500464747-JHA-Sep2006.pdf>

- 5) Maulana Wahiduddin Khan, Prof. Farida Khanam, Translated the Quran, 2019, Center for Peace and Spirituality 1, Nizamuddin West Market, p 36, surat albaqarati: 285.
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- 7) Jack S. Levy; T. Clifton Morgan, the Frequency and Seriousness of War: An Inverse Relationship? The Journal of Conflict Resolution, Vol. 28, No. 4. (Dec., 1984), pp. 731-749. <http://fas-polisci.rutgers.edu/levy/articles/1984%20Frequency%20&%20Seriousness%20of%20War.pdf>
- 8) aleamiriu, al'iielam bimanaqib al'iislami, 78-79.
- 9) tah, eabd alrahman, soal al'akhlaqi, aldaar albayda': almarkaz althaqafii alearabia, t 1, 2000, 14.
- 10) muhamad eali altaskhiri, alqiam al'iinsaniat almushtarakat wadawruha fi taeziz altadamun bayn alshueub wal'ummi, kitab alhiwar mae aldhdat walakhir, almajmae alealamiu liltaqrib bayn almadhahib al'iislamiati, tahrn, 2005, 125.
- 11) aleamiriu, al'iielam bimanaqib al'iislami, 78-79.
- 12) Chile Eboe-Osuji, Grave Breaches' As War Crimes: Much Ado about ...'Serious Violations'? <https://www.icc-cpi.int/NR/rdonlyres/827EE9EC-5095-48C0-AB04-E38686EE9A80/283279/GRAVEBREACHESMUCHADOABOUTSERIOUSVIOLATIONS.pdf>
- 13) Kant, 'iimanuil, almabadi al'asasiat limitafizya' al'akhlaqi, halba: dar alsharqa, tarjamat hikmat hamsi, taqdim eadil alewwa.
- 14) Aleamiriu, al'iielam bimanaqib al'iislami, 80.
- 15) Himself.
- 16) Eabd alrahman, soal al'akhlaqi, 15.
- 17) Guy Riddihough, Gilbert Chin, Elizabeth Culotta, Barbara Jasny, Leslie Roberts, Sacha Vignieri, Human Conflict: Winning the Peace, Science 18 May 2012, <https://science.sciencemag.org/content/336/6083/818>
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- 18) Kant, almabadi al'asasiat limitafizya' al'akhlaqi.
- 19) Eabd alrahman, soal al'akhlaqi, 16.
- 20) Dr. Keith F. Otterbin (1936-2015) was Professor Emeritus of Anthropology at the University of Buffalo (SUNYAB) in the United States. Dr. Otterbein was a former Head of Human Relations Area Files and a frequent contributor to cross-cultural research, primarily on war-related topics. Otterbin is the author of How War Began (2004), in which he explores the origins of war in human society. He passed away on June 17, 2015 at the age of 79.
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- 22) Altaskhiri, alqiam al'iinsaniat, 129.
- 23) Lou Marinof, Biological Roots of Human Conflict, Submitted: July 2014, <http://journal-of-conflictology.uoc.edu/joc/ca/index.php/journal-of-conflictology/index.html>
- 24) Stephen A. LeBlanc (born 1943) is an American archaeologist and former director of collections at Harvard University's Peabody Museum of Archeology and Ethnology. He is the author of several books on the archeology of the southwestern United States and prehistoric warfare. His books fought the widespread idea of pacifist prehistoric cultures. <http://village.anth.wsu.edu/user/7>
- 25) R. Brian Ferguson, War Is Not Part of Human Nature, scientific american, September 1, 2018, <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/war-is-not-part-of-human-nature/>

- 26) Yoshihiro Francis Fukuyama (born October 27, 1952) is an American scientist, philosopher, political economist, author, and university professor. He is best known for his 1992 book *The End of History and the Last Man*, in which he argued that the spread of liberal, capitalist, and free-market democracies across the world may mark the end point of human social, cultural, and political development. Fukuyama was associated with the neo-conservatives, but he distanced himself from them in later periods.
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- 27) James Bradley Thayer was born on January 15, 1831, in Haver Hill, USA, and died on February 14, 1902.
- 28) Altashiri, *alqiam al'iinsaniat*, 123.
- 29) Quoted from *Rabat Andalusia pamphlets: Center for Andalusian Studies and Dialogue of Civilizations, Edition 1, 2006*, Arabic section, pp. 38-39; French Section, pp. 38-39.
- 30) <https://www.un.org/en charter-united-nations/index.html>
- 31) Gustavo De Carvalho, Active participation is needed if Africa is to claim its rightful role in the UN's peacebuilding architecture review in 2015, 17 DEC 2014, <https://issafrica.org/iss-today/africa-must-shape-international-peacebuilding>
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- 33) Altashiri, *alqiam al'iinsaniat*, 133.
- 34) The keys to preventing conflict between countries, 22 Nov 2018, <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2018/11/how-to-prevent-conflict/>
- 35) Center for Andalusian Studies, pp. 40.
- 36) Frank Fredericks, Here's how we put an end to violent conflict, World Economic Forum, 18 Apr 2018, <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2018/04/heres-how-we-put-an-end-to-violent-conflict-2901d1f8-8fdc-4db7-b500-4ea539c29b65>
- 37) Center for Andalusian Studies, pp. 41.
- 38) Altashiri, *alqiam al'iinsaniat*, 134.
- 39) Pierre Perrin, The impact of humanitarian aid on conflict development, *International Review of the Red Cross*, 30-06-1998, <https://www.icrc.org/en/doc/resources/documents/article/other/57jpcj.htm>
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https://www.bibelwissenschaft.de/fileadmin/buh_bibelmodul/media/wibi/pdf/Schwangerschaft__2018-09-20_06_20.pdf
- 44) Jeremiah, 1: 4-5.

- 45) He sees when we walk or lie down. In short, he is constantly watching us. None of our ways are hidden from him. He knows what we're about to say before we even open our mouths. He knows the future as he knows the past and the present. William MacDonald, *Believer's Bible Commentary - Old and New Testament in Vietnamese Language*, Christian Reading Room, Hong Kong SAR of China, 2004.
- 46) This is what one can say about the existence of an omnipresent God. David now turns to the question of the strength and skill of the Lord. He chose the example of the wonderful development of the fetus in its mother's womb. A liquid item smaller than the point on this, already contains all the characteristics of an unborn child, the color of his skin, his eyes, his hair, the shape of his face, and the skills he would have. Everything that the child will be physically and mentally present in is the germ of the fertilized egg. You will generate: 60 trillion cells, 170,000 kilometers of nerve fibers, 102,000 kilometers of blood vessels that supply the entire human body, and 250 bones, not to mention the joints, ligaments and muscles. (88) David describes the formation of the fetus. Intensely sharp and hairy. "You made my kidneys, and bound me together in my mother's womb. God shaped each of our organs. Each one is a marvel in how it works. Think, for example, of the brain with its ability to record facts, sounds, smells, shapes, tactile impressions, pain, And his ability to remember, his ability to make calculations, his almost unlimited ability to make decisions and solve problems that God has wove us in the womb of our mother This is the exact description of what goes on in the formation of muscles, tendons, ligaments, nerves, blood vessels and bones of the human skeleton, David explodes in praise For God. Thinking of man, the crown of creation, he cannot fail to realize that he is a wonderful creature. The more we think about the wonders of the human body, the ruling system, its complexity, its beauty, its instincts and its inherited factors, the more we are amazed that natural scientists are not more convinced by the belief in this infinite Creator. jurj busta, *qamus alkitaab almuqdas*, bayrut, 1894, *mujalad2*, s 451.
- 47) The psalmist goes back to those times when his body was growing in the womb. Note that he uses the personal pronoun *je* and the possessive adjective *Mon* to denote fetus or fetus. This is the indication that the human personality is present before birth in the Bible. Therefore, abortion is murder, except in cases of dire medical necessity, for David knew very well that God knew him from the beginning. His body, his skeleton, was not hidden from God when it was made in a secret place, woven into the depths of the earth. Obviously, this expression does not mean working underground, because no one was trained there. In this context, David says simply "in the womb". We find a similar way of expressing it in Ephesians 4:9 which states that Christ descended into the lower regions of the earth. From context, this is Jesus' coming into this world through the antechamber of the Virgin's womb. Thus Paul refers to the incarnation. Di.yusuf eid, *mawsueat aladyan alsamawiat walwadeiati*, ta1, 1995, s 91.
- 48) When the psalmist talks about a "formless mass" he is referring to something tightly coiled or coiled. For Barnes and others, the phrase is most appropriate for a fetus or fetus "all of its limbs are somehow twisted and immature, that is, before they take their characteristic shape. And proportions. While the joyful anthem of Israel was in this primal form of its existence, the eyes of God saw it. And in the Book of God, The whole days of David's life were recorded by the divine architect, before the time, the date when the baby David let out his first cry. Ben Witherington III - *Torah Old and New_ Exegesis, Intertextuality, and Hermeneutics*-Fortress Press, 2018, P: 85.
- 49) God's counsels about us and our well-being are as profound as the unknowable. We cannot think of the number of mercies we have received from him. It will help us to remain in the fear of the Lord all day long, if, when we wake up in the morning, our first thoughts are of Him: how to admire and bless our God for his precious salvation, when we wake up in the world of glory! Certainly we must not use our organs and our senses, designed with great curiosity, as instruments of iniquity for sin. But our immortal and rational souls are a more noble and gifted act of God. Yet, had it not been for his precious thoughts of our love, our mind and life would forever, through our sins, prove the occasion of our eternal misery. How then can we rejoice in contemplating God's love for sinners through Jesus Christ, the sum of which exceeds every account! Sin is hated, and sinners mourn for all who fear the Lord. But while we avoid them we must pray for them; With God they can be converted and saved. Since the Lord knows us well, and we are strangers to ourselves, we must desperately desire and pray that

we may be sought and confirmed by His Word and Spirit. If there is an evil way in me, let me see it; and you are you. The path of piety is pleasing to God and beneficial to us. It ends in eternal life. It's the good old fashioned way. All the saints desire to be preserved and led in this way, so that they will not miss it, or go out of it, or tire of it. The psalmist reflects on the universality with which God created his body, soul, and spirit. How not to hack your thoughts. Attention to the smallest details. Almost without exception, says Andrew Ivey, every cell 'knows' its role in fulfilling God's purpose for the well-being of the body as a whole. William MacDonald, Believer's Bible Commentary.

- 50) Psalmist, 139: 13-17.
- 51) Blessed is the man who fills his quiver with it: Despite the recent outpouring of propaganda against big families, God bless the man who has a quiver full of children. But again, it is clear that these are the sons of believers, members of a family that has faith. Otherwise, older children can be a source of great grief for the parents. "He will not be ashamed when his sons talk to the enemies at the door." F. Meyer notes that the besieged army and the besieged army met at the city gate. The thought in this verse is as follows: A man's children defend him in civil or legal matters so that he does not suffer any loss or injury. They see that justice has been served. And the psalm wonderfully proves the sincerity of the word of the Lord through the mouth of Zacharias: "Not by force or by force, but by my spirit," says the Lord of the worlds. Hosts. We are always in danger of putting our trust in the dollar, the euro, or human ingenuity. But it is not by these means that the will of the Lord is fulfilled. And in his spirit we work toward eternity. What remains is not what we accomplish for God with our own resources, but what God does through us in His great power. We can only make wood, straw and straw. He can use us in the production of gold, silver and precious stones. When we act on our own, we stand idly by. On the other hand, if we are called upon by God, He makes our lives fruitful. Physical weapons produce bodily fruits. Spiritual weapons produce spiritual fruits Psalm 128: The blessing of the Lord. Thomas Newberry, This work is generally known as The Englishman's Bible, London, 1890, Revelation.
- 52) Psalmist, 127: 3-5.
- 53) Joachim Lauer, Suizid, Das wissenschaftliche Bibellexikon im
- 54) Internet, Aug. 2012, <https://www.bibelwissenschaft.de/stichwort/28321/>
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- 57) Psalms, 139:16.
- 58) Corinthians 2, 5:6-8.
- 59) James, 5:14-15.
- 60) Corinthians 2, 4:16-18.
- 61) Sahih 'abi dawud, alraqam: 3052.
- 62) Surat almayidati: 5.

- 63) Al-Bayhaqi narrated it in "Shu'ab al-Iman" (5/296) (6706), its Iraqi chain of transmission was weakened in "Takhrij al-Ihya" (3/186), and he said in another place (2/221): Its men are trustworthy, and Al-Albani said in ((Silsilat al-Ahadith al-Sahihah) (3420): Its chain of narrators is good, and its men are trustworthy.
- 64) Rawah 'abu dawud.
- 65) Rawah 'abu dawud.
- 66) Surat almumtahanati: 8.
- 67) Rawah 'abu dawud.
- 68) surat al'iisra'i: 36.
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- 71) Ibn Abd al-Hakam, Abu al-Qasim Abd al-Rahman Ibn Abd Allah Abd al-Hakam Ibn Aayn al-Qurashi the Egyptian; Investigation: Muhammad Al-Hujairi (1416 AH - 1996 AD). The Conquest of Egypt and its News (1st ed.). Beirut - Lebanon: Dar Al-Fikr, p4.
- 72) Surat Al-Nahl: 93.
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- 32) bin eabd alhakama, 'abu alqasim ebd alrhmn bin eabd allah ebd alhakam bin aeyun alqurshy almsry; tahqiq: muhammad alhujiyry (1416h - 1996mu). futuh misr wa'akhbaruha (altabeat al'uwlaa). bayrut - lubnan: dar alfikri.
- 33) jims bradli thayar hu muhami 'amrikiun, wulid fi 15 yanayir 1831, fi hafir hil fi alwilayat almutahidati, watuufiy fi 14 fibrayir 1902.
- 34) tahi, eabd alrahman, sual al'akhlaqi, aldaar albayda'i: almarkaz althaqafii alearabia, t 1, 2000.
- 35) aleamari, 'abu alhasani, al'iielam bimanaqib al'iislami, alqahirata: dar alkitaab alearabii, 1387/1967(dirasat watahqiq 'ahmad eabd alhamid ghrab).
- 36) ean "kirasat 'andalusia" alribati: markaz dirasat al'andalus wahiwar alhadarati, t 1, 2006, alqism alearabii.
- 37) qamus alkitaab almuqdasi, jurj busti, bayrut, 1894, mujaladi2.
- 38) alquran alkarim.
- 39) alkitab almiqdasi.
- 40) muhamad eali altaskhiri, alqiam al'iinsaniat almushtarakat wadawruha fi taeziz altadamun bayn alshueub wal'ummi, kitab alhiwar mae aldhdhat walakhir, almajmae alealamiu liltaqrib bayn almadhahib al'iislamiati, tahrn, 2005.
- 41) almuafaqat lishatibi: ji2.
- 42) musueat aladian alsamawiat walwadeiati, di.yusuf eid, ta1, 1995.